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Abstract

This report is a deliverable for the project MegaRoller – Developing the PTO of the first MW-level Oscillating Wave Surge Converter. The report outlines the potential commercial applications of the developed technology and reviews the existing markets as well as forecast future demand for these applications.

Two business cases are presented for the developed solution in European markets, one for the production of electricity and the other for the production of green hydrogen. The elements related to the underlying cost benefit analysis are presented and the limitations of the analysis is discussed.

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List of Abbreviations

AEL	alkaline electrolysis
CSP	concentrated solar power
FOAK	First-of-a-kind
FIT	feed-in tariff
GW	gigawatt
kW	kilowatts
LCOE	levelized cost of energy
MW	megawatts
MWh	megawatt-hour
OWSC	oscillating wave surge converter
PEM	polymer electrolyte membrane
PPA	power purchase agreement
PTO	power take-off
PV	solar photovoltaics
RO	reverse osmosis
TW	terawatt
TWh	terawatt-hours
VRE	variable renewable energy
WEC	wave energy converter

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

MegaRoller is a collaborative research and innovation project for increasing the competitiveness and commercialization of wave energy. The project has focused on scale-up and improvement of technology that can capture and convert the power of ocean waves into usable energy. This solution is the MegaRoller wave energy conversion device, representing the most advanced technical solution for the industrialization of wave energy.

The total theoretical wave energy resource around the world is more than 30 000 TWh/yr¹, which offers significant opportunities for increasing the share of renewable energy production and reducing the reliance on fossil fuels. Through replacement of emissions in the production of electricity and hydrogen we estimate the total annual emissions savings potential of the MegaRoller technology at 517 million metric tons (megaton) of carbon-dioxide equivalent emissions, representing roughly 1 % of the global greenhouse gas emissions.

Generation schedule of the MegaRoller WEC is distinct compared to the variability of wind and PV power generation, thus it can be used to complement other variable renewable energy (VRE) sources in energy systems aiming for deep decarbonization. The internal energy storage capacity of the technology, primarily used to smoothen variable power input from the waves, can be further exploited to provide fast frequency regulation services to the power system. The consistent and controllable power output of the MegaRoller also provides an excellent base for feeding continuous industrial processes.

The single most efficient application of the MegaRoller technology for reducing carbon emissions is in a dedicated green hydrogen production system, in combination with other renewable energy sources, to displace emissions from transportation. With possible sites assessed in 20 countries around the world, the annual potential production from the MegaRoller dedicated green hydrogen scheme exceeds 5 megatons of green hydrogen.

Considering today's electricity demand in larger industrialized countries with a suitable wave energy resource, the total addressable market for the MegaRoller technology is roughly 2 600 TWh/yr. With steep requirements for decarbonization and the increasing demand of electricity the market will increase to 3 700 TWh/yr by 2050. Expanding the analysis of market potential to all countries with an applicable wave energy resource and a sufficient power demand, the total quantity of MegaRoller WECs to satisfy the serviceable market would surmount to 70 000 units.

Within the scope of the MegaRoller project two business cases were developed for the MegaRoller WEC. The first case analysed an 8 MW MegaRoller WEC farm in Ireland, producing electricity to the wholesale markets and participating in the Irish frequency reserve markets. The wave farm would generate approximately 19 200 MWh of electricity per year and generate an annual income in the range of EUR 2.9–4.1 million resulting in a relatively high rate of return for the project.

The second case investigated the potential of the MegaRoller technology in the production of green hydrogen and seawater desalination, industries which are both struggling with sustainability issues. The system was considered for Portugal and consisted of a 5 MW MegaRoller WEC farm, a 5 MW PV plant, and 5 MW of electrolyzer capacity. The annual output of this energy hub is 350 metric tons of hydrogen, with the addition of 1 200 MWh of electricity dispatched to the Portuguese electricity markets. The annual income from the sales of hydrogen and electricity would range between EUR 1.8–3.6 million.

¹ Mørk, G. et al. (2010) Assessing the Global Wave Energy Potential

The advantages of the MegaRoller technology were highlighted in hydrogen production. A capacity factor of almost 50 % was achieved for the electrolysis, which is significant improvement to the 30–35 % typical for system powered only by solar PV. Requirements for oversizing the power generation capacity were reduced, and as more consistent power could be provided for the electrolysis, the lifetime and performance of the electrolyzer stacks were increased.

The presented cases serve to demonstrate the commercial opportunities of the MegaRoller technology in relation to the production of renewable electricity and hydrogen, already at a relatively small-scale. Throughout the MegaRoller project further opportunities for the technology have also been identified in the production of freshwater through desalination of seawater, in providing frequency support services for grid operators, and in applications in other wave energy conversion technologies.

The purpose of this deliverable is to present the commercial applications for the technology and demonstrate its value in the two business cases. Costing information is presented in detail in a separate confidential report *D5.6 LCC assessment report of the MegaRoller device*, and this has formed the basis for the data used in this report and for deliverable *D6.11 LCOE report* which presents the LCOE for the solution, including a more detailed description of the project results in terms of electricity production.

The MegaRoller project has focused on the core technical component of the MegaRoller WEC which is the power take-off unit. Further efforts are required to develop the remaining system and realize the value generated through the project as well as the broader impacts and potential of the MegaRoller technology.

1 INTRODUCTION

Wave energy represents a significant opportunity in decarbonizing energy production. The estimates of total potential for electricity production vary² from 4 000 TWh/yr to 32 000 TWh/yr however, the scale of the opportunity is undeniable. To date the industrialization of wave energy has been very limited due to technical challenges and limitations in scale resulting in comparatively high cost of electricity production. There are numerous types of wave energy converters (WEC) in development designed to unlock this potential, but the oscillating wave surge converter technology type (OWSC) has distinct advantages³ over all other solutions and represents the most advanced technical solution for the industrialization of wave energy.

The MegaRoller is a European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme -funded project to increase the efficiency and reliability of OWSC technologies thereby decreasing the cost of production and facilitating their commercialization. The project is a consortium effort by ten independent European partners from four countries which was initiated in 2018 and concludes in 2021. In particular, the project has focused on the hardware and control algorithm of the power take-off (PTO) for an OWSC with an aim to design, build and validate a system for 1 MW WEC. The set target for the project was to decrease the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) for next generation OWSC devices below 150 EUR/MWh.

During the project, various aspects that support this target were worked on, including:

- Improving overall PTO design, including operation of a test bench
- Development of hydraulic cylinders and accumulator arrangement to maximise efficiency and reliability
- Developing wave-by-wave prediction software and wave-structure interaction models
- Advancing the efficiency control and energy storage control software
- Development of supervisor control software

The industrialization of the technology and the business cases presented in this report are primarily considered in the context of the MegaRoller WEC device. Therefore, in parallel to the MegaRoller project and the development of the PTO, the remaining technology components for the 1 MW WEC device have been conceptualized. The technology and the WEC device are described in chapter 2.

The MegaRoller technology introduces various advantages in decarbonizing energy production and through its unique characteristics can be applied in multiple energy-intensive industrial processes. The MegaRoller can be used for the production of electricity and hydrogen as well as for the supply of freshwater. In addition, the technology can provide frequency regulation services for grid operators. These markets and the potential impact of the MegaRoller technology are described in chapter 3.

Two business cases for the application of the MegaRoller WEC are presented in chapter 4. Case A focuses on direct electricity supply in Ireland and Case B on the production of green hydrogen in Portugal. The revenue model and estimates of annual income are provided. The cost-benefit elements related to the analysis are further presented in chapter 5 and the limitation discussed in chapter 6.

² Cruz (2008). Ocean Wave Energy; IPCC (2011) Renewable Energy Sources and Climate Change Mitigation

³ Chang et al (2016) Numerical modelling of the effects of wave energy converter characteristics on nearshore wave conditions

2 MEGAROLLER TECHNOLOGY AND WEC DEVICE

2.1 Technology description

Wave energy captured by WECs is essentially concentrated solar radiation cumulated and amplified over vast distances across the oceans. The volumetric amount of energy becomes more concentrated as solar radiation translates through temperature differences into winds and further into waves with winds blowing along the ocean surface.

OWSC technologies use a bottom-hinged oscillating panel which follows the surge movement of the water particles in the nearshore area, in water depths between 10 and 25 metres. The surge phenomenon is a universal physical event that occurs when waves approach the shoreline. Waves in deep water are water particles moving in a circular motion. As waves approach the shore, they start shoaling as some of the water particles moving in a circular motion meet the seabed. This interaction with the seabed elongates the circular motion into a horizontal elliptic shape which, in turn amplifies the horizontal movement of the water particles in the near-shore area, creating a strong surge zone.

The MegaRoller WEC unit is based on WaveRoller technology commercialized by AW-Energy. The device is anchored to the seabed and depending on tidal conditions it is mostly or fully submerged. A horizontal panel is affixed to the device which moves back and forth following the movement of the waves. The movement of the panel is transmitted through a drivetrain into a PTO which further converts the wave induced oscillations from mechanical energy to electricity.

Figure 1 MegaRoller WEC unit

The MegaRoller PTO consists of two cylinder units and a standardized power unit. As the panel moves, the PTO's hydraulic pistons pump hydraulic fluids inside a closed hydraulic circuit inside a hermetic structure. These cylinders are composed of single action pistons, one cylinder acting when the panel moves towards the coast, and another when the movement has the opposite direction.

These high-pressure fluids are fed into a hydraulic motor that drives an electricity generator. The cylinders use the mechanical power applied to the pistons to compress the hydraulic fluid and store it in the accumulators that help to smoothen the variation of the power produced. The energy stored in the accumulators is transferred through pressurized hydraulic flow to a hydraulic motor, followed by an electric generator that converts it into electrical energy. The electrical output is then connected to substation at shore and subsequently for further usage.

2.2 Potential commercial applications

2.2.1 Production of renewable electricity

In continuation of the preceding 350 kW WaveRoller technology, the MegaRoller technology is designed for the production of electrical energy. The development of the PTO hardware solution, the control system, and algorithms in the scope of the MegaRoller project form a part of the envisioned 1 MW WEC. In addition to the PTO, the remaining technology components for a 1 MW device have simultaneously been conceptualized. Through further development of the MegaRoller WEC system in its entirety, the technology is intended to be used in dedicated wave energy projects. Due to its large unit capacity the MegaRoller WEC enables efficient utilization of wave resource in sites with highly energetic wave conditions. The energy can be efficiently captured even from the most energetic waves as the maximum moment of MegaRoller panel with its two PTOs is up to 9 MNm. Thus, the mechanical capacity of the technology is more than doubled compared to the latest technology.

Electricity generated by MegaRoller technology could be used to decarbonize existing power systems especially in the vicinity of continental shorelines. As the MegaRoller devices are submerged, the technology has a minimal impact on the surrounding landscape and due to the density of the energy resource the overall physical footprint of the projects much smaller than in comparison to other VRE technologies. The MegaRoller devices can be located relatively close to coastal cities leading to reduced investment requirements and technical challenges related to power transmission management. This is especially important as majority of the human habitat and electricity consumption are in coastal areas.

2.2.2 Production of green hydrogen

In addition to direct electricity supply, the MegaRoller technology can provide value-add in the production of green hydrogen using water electrolysis. Hydrogen is expected to contribute to decarbonization across various industries including energy production, transportation, and manufacturing industries. However, for hydrogen to efficiently displace fossil emissions the production must be powered fully by renewable electricity - i.e. classified as green hydrogen.

The lowest cost of renewable electricity generation is currently achieved by onshore solar and onshore wind, both of which are intermittent and dependant on a strong grid connection. Producing hydrogen with these intermittent power sources requires either a significant energy storage investment or fast reacting polymer electrolyte membrane electrolysis technology (PEM) which is currently more costly than an alkaline hydrogen electrolyser (AEL), the most mature and least cost solution for green hydrogen production⁴. The MegaRoller technology provides several unique benefits that resolve these challenges and add value in the production of green hydrogen which will be presented here.

Increased hydrogen production

The key differentiating factor for the MegaRoller technology in a green hydrogen production scheme is its distinct production schedule. In various locations the production profile of MegaRoller is complementary to that of solar and wind production on a both hourly and seasonal basis. In particular, the value is notable in combination with solar PV as the wave resource is greatest during wintertime and there is also production during night-time. Additionally, MegaRoller can suppress short-term power fluctuation in power systems through its inbuilt energy storage capacity. The annual capacity factor that can be

⁶ European Commission DG-Energy (2020) Hydrogen generation in Europe: Overview of key costs and benefits

achieved using combination of MegaRoller wave energy plant and PV plant can exceed 60 % with moderate generation capacity oversizing, while purely PV powered electrolysis typically reaches capacity factor of 30–35 % even with significant oversizing. Hence, a MegaRoller wave farm can increase the system utilization and produce more hydrogen per electrolysis capacity.

Reduced capital expenditure for industrial processes

Seasonal variability in hydrogen production also impacts the investment cost of a plant if the consumption is inflexible. This is the case especially with industrial processes, which are currently highly inflexible both to maximize productivity and due to technical restrictions. Thus, large seasonal variation may induce requirements for significant storage capacity, which significantly increase system costs. In these cases - where MegaRoller complements seasonal generation variation and result in relatively constant hydrogen production over the year - the total investment costs can be reduced.

Reduced operational expenditure the electrolysis equipment

Furthermore, the influence of dynamic operating mode (i.e. responsiveness to VRE power supply) to the degradation rate of the electrolyzer stacks is a major concern considering green hydrogen applications. The degradation of both alkaline electrolysis (AEL) and polymer electrolyte membrane (PEM) electrolysis has been studied by various groups during recent years⁵. For AEL it has been shown that both dynamic operating conditions as well as start-up and shutdowns increase the degradation rate of the stacks. The catalyst at the electrode surface deteriorates due to varying cell potential and current density. Additionally, the low-voltage conditions occurring at start-up and shutdown transients amplifies the electrode degradation pace.

Degradation of PEM cells due to power fluctuation seems to be a much less understood phenomenon. It has been found that the performance of PEM cells may actually increase when the cells are subjected to load variation. However, the testing periods for both studies were relatively short: only 500 and 1009 hours, respectively⁶. One clear reason for performance improvement is the fluoride dissolution from the membrane caused by the dynamic load. As the membrane thins out, the ohmic resistance decreases reducing ohmic losses. However, at commercial operating times, membrane thinning could become problematic due to increased gas crossover and operational safety issues. This would most likely reduce the lifetime of the electrolyzer stack in commercial use.

Stacks contribute to significant share of water electrolyzer costs. Therefore, it would be highly beneficial to form as stable as possible operating conditions to the electrolyzer to reduce the number of required stack replacements and related costs. For example, PEM electrolyzer stacks typically contribute between 33–42 % of the electrolyzer system capital expenditures⁷. Therefore, every stack replacement during the investment lifetime has significant impact on the life cycle costs.

Increased stability of power supply provided by MegaRoller can therefore potentially reduce the number of replacements by several iterations depending on the lifetime of the investment.

⁵ Kuroda, Y. et al. (2019) Self-repairing hybrid nanosheet anode catalysts for alkaline water electrolysis connected with fluctuating renewable energy; Uchino, Y. et al. (2018) Relationship between the redox reactions on a bipolar plate and reverse current after alkaline water electrolysis; Rakousky, C. et al. (2017) Polymer electrolyte membrane water electrolysis: Restraining degradation in the presence of fluctuating power

⁶ Frensch, S. et al. (2019) Influence of the operation mode on PEM water electrolysis degradation

⁷ NREL (2019) Manufacturing cost analysis for proton exchange membrane water electrolyzers

Reduced hydrogen transportation costs

Another significant advantage of the MegaRoller technology in relation to green hydrogen production is also its natural environment close to shorelines. As heavy industries are conventionally situated in ports, power generation and thus, hydrogen production can be located close to the consumption.

Alternative energy sources like PV and onshore wind power have a significant land footprint, which might exclude in-situ power generation and green hydrogen production completely. Power generation farther away from the H₂ production also generates drastically higher requirements for the transmission grid. Locating the entire hydrogen production system inland creates a long distance to the point of consumption and increases the requirements for transportation logistics.

2.2.3 Water desalination with reverse osmosis

The near-shore operating environment of MegaRoller is beneficial also in a water desalination process, which is in large parts based on reverse osmosis (RO) technology. RO systems are widely used in arid areas to purify and desalinate sea water and provide local areas with a fresh water supply. However, the RO process is relatively energy intensive, and the existing systems are powered mostly with fossil-based power from the utility grid, which raises concerns of the sustainability of RO.

Like most current industrial processes, RO isn't designed to operate in variable operating conditions, and the decarbonization of these processes with wind and solar power would result in highly variable power supply, leading to variable operating conditions. As water consumption in most areas is relatively inflexible, the variation in freshwater output will also lead to water storage requirements. As with the electrolyzer stacks, the lifetime of the RO membrane is also significantly reduced with fluctuating operation⁸. The MegaRoller technology can therefore bring additional value also to water desalination by balancing the power supply, and leading to more stable operating conditions, more consistent freshwater output, and reduced storage requirements and operational costs. The implementation of the MegaRoller technology in a RO process also remains closer to conventional RO plant as the variation of MegaRoller power input to the system is very slow.

The MegaRoller has also infrastructural synergies with water desalination, being located in the near-shore environment. For RO projects, water intake and brine disposal commonly contribute to a significant share of the project costs. When a MegaRoller wave farm is used to power the RO plant, the required offshore infrastructure of the two sub systems could be built and installed together leading to significant cost reductions. For example, the brine discharge pipe could be connected to a subsea cable of MegaRoller, which can be installed together.

2.2.4 Frequency support services

As the amount of wind and PV in power systems increase and conventional thermal power plants are simultaneously decommissioned, the capability for active power management reduces and the grid becomes more vulnerable to load and generation transients. When the balance between power generation and consumption is disturbed, the imbalance is realized as changing frequency. The frequency starts to decrease when consumption exceeds generation and vice versa. Significant variation in grid frequency is a serious issue as it can cause damage to grid connected equipment. A MegaRoller wave

⁸ Mito, M. et al. (2019) Reverse osmosis (ro) membrane desalination driven by wind and solar photovoltaic (pv) energy: state of the art and challenges for large-scale implementation

power plant can contribute to frequency stability and operational security of the power system by managing its power output according to the grid requirements.

If an increase in grid frequency is observed, caused by generation exceeding consumption, MegaRollers can ramp down their power generation. Additionally, in contrast to wind and PV technologies, MegaRollers are also capable of ramping up power generation by using their in-built energy storage capacity. Energy stored in the accumulators of the MegaRoller PTO can be exploited for a short-term boost in power generation. The response time in power generation is excellent, rivalling that of a grid connected battery energy storage systems.

The power regulation capabilities of MegaRoller depend on the resource conditions and the momentary power output. For example, if the power output is close to nominal production of the system, there is significant potential in downregulation of generation output while upregulation capacity is reduced. Similarly, the upregulation potential is the most significant during modest wave conditions.

The electricity markets for frequency support services vary by country and electrical grid, whereby some systems have little to no dedicated structure to highly developed schemes of multiple market instruments for power frequency support. On the other hand, some countries have already developed a sophisticated marketplace consisting of various frequency management products with different technical requirements. Nevertheless, due to its fast response capabilities MegaRoller WECs can participate in all short-term frequency containment markets.

A relevant case example for MegaRoller is Ireland, where the local transmission system operator has a payment scheme for a range of system services. The grid codes and electricity markets in Ireland have been adapting to the transition of traditional power systems dominated by synchronized units to power systems with high shares of variable renewable generation. In this way, new market regulations consider the possible contribution from variable renewable generation in a variety of system services⁹, including frequency support services. The hydraulic accumulator capacity of the MegaRoller is well suited to provide short-term active power response in the range of a several seconds, which fits with the fast frequency reserve service in Ireland and may also enable for eventual future virtual inertia services.

2.2.5 Application in other wave energy conversion technologies

Translating large torque levels into grid compliant electricity is one of the main challenges that many wave energy technology developers face when scaling up. For example, in 2020 the developers behind the Mocean WEC described this challenge clearly: “Hinged rafts typically have small angular rotational responses to waves (less than 10° arcs). As power for a hinged raft is the product of torque and hinge velocity, large torque levels are required, which leads to an expensive PTO system¹⁰. Many developers have not ventured down the path of hydraulic PTOs due to the perception of high cost and low efficiency. However, the MegaRoller project has demonstrated that when addressing the complete path of energy transfer from wave to smooth grid electricity, the MegaRoller PTO is a cost effective, reliable and an efficient technical solution.

The MegaRoller PTO is not solely applicable in the oscillating wave surge converter type device, and the MegaRoller WEC, but can also be applied to other wave energy converters and thus enable other WECs to

⁹ Gaffney, F. et al. (2019) Reconciling high renewable electricity ambitions with market economics and system operation: Lessons from Ireland's power system

¹⁰ McNatt, J. & Retzler, C. (2020) The performance of the Mocean M100 wave energy converter described through numerical and physical modelling

harness larger forces and consequently produce larger power levels when scaled up. By scaling up the power levels, the cost of electricity of wave energy farms can be reduced through reducing the number of units and the reducing the balance of plant costs per megawatt of installed capacity. Thus, MegaRoller has a wider benefit to the wave energy industry by enabling larger devices and directly reducing the cost of energy.

In addition, the MegaRoller PTO contains several other innovations that can enhance a WEC beyond high power levels. These include counter force tuning, wave prediction, and a full-scale test bench. The ability to adjust the counterforce to match the oncoming waves in order to increase the motion of the prime mover will generate high energy yields from lower sea states. By predicting oncoming waves, a WEC can ramp up or down the power levels before the wave arrives and participate in the frequency support market.

3 MARKET FOR THE MEGAROLLER TECHNOLOGY

3.1 European policy framework

The actions taken to mitigate carbon emissions in energy production have enabled the rapid emergence of non-conventional technologies in renewable energy generation. The installed capacity of solar PV and onshore wind alone have increased over 930 GW over the past decade. Other sources of renewable electricity production have also increased including bioenergy, geothermal, hydropower, CSP and offshore wind. In total 1,3 TW of new renewable capacity was installed between 2009 and 2019¹¹ with around 11 % of energy being extracted from renewable sources globally¹² and 19,7 % in the European Union¹³. However, in Europe the European Green Deal calls for faster cleansing of the energy system, targeting 40 % of renewable energy by 2040.

The European Green Deal – a roadmap for making the EU’s economy sustainable – was presented in December 2019¹⁴. This was followed by a variety of investment and action plans during 2020, including a strategy for boosting offshore renewable energy.

At a high level, the EU Green deal provides an action plan to

1. Boost the efficient use of resources by moving to a clean, circular economy
2. Restore biodiversity and cut pollution

In relation to ocean wave energy, a supportive policy to the Green Deal, the European Offshore Renewable Energy Strategy¹⁵ sets a target of 100 MW for ocean energy deployments by 2025 and around 1 GW by 2030, mainly stemming from wave and tidal projects. The strategy envisions a significant contribution from the technologies particularly in supporting grid stability. Furthermore, the European advocacy group for ocean energy estimates that by 2050 the deployments of wave and tidal technologies could reach up to 100 GW for the continent, supplying 10 % of the total electricity demand and resulting in 400 000 European jobs¹⁶.

Furthermore, the European Commission has set a strategic objective to install 6 GW of green hydrogen capacity by 2024 and by 2030 at least 40 GW within Europe and 40 GW in Europe’s neighbourhood with export to the EU¹⁷, marking hydrogen as a key priority to achieve the European Green Deal and Europe’s clean energy transition. In addition to the 40 GW, the investment projects assume 500 GW of renewable electrolyzers by 2050. With highly ambitious policy support around the world, hydrogen could meet up to 24 % total energy demand by 2050 annually requiring 31 320 TWh of electricity from renewable energy sources¹⁸.

At the same time as these actions for a greener future in the EU were being worked on, the world was impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. Significant public funds were directed towards supporting economies both during and after the pandemic, and there was a strong focus on ensuring these funds

¹¹ IEA (2019) Renewable capacity growth worldwide stalled in 2018 after two decades of strong expansion

¹² Our World in Data, Renewable Energy

¹³ Eurostat, Renewable energy statistics

¹⁴ European Commission (2019) The European Green Deal sets out how to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050

¹⁵ European Commission (2020) An EU Strategy to harness the potential of offshore renewable energy for a climate neutral future

¹⁶ Ocean Energy Europe, Powered by the ocean

¹⁷ European Commission (2020) A hydrogen strategy for a climate-neutral Europe

¹⁸ Bloomberg New Energy Finance (2020) Hydrogen Economy Outlook

also supported the green objectives. As part of the EUR 1.8 trillion stimulus package from the EU, at least 30 % of the funds will be committed towards fighting climate change.

The MegaRoller project is well aligned with these European policy objectives. Improving a new form of renewable energy technology assists in the move towards a clean economy, while the low lifetime carbon impact supports a circular economy.

3.2 Emissions reduction potential

The total theoretical wave energy resource around the world is more than 30 000 TWh/year¹⁹, which represents significant opportunity for increasing the share of renewable energy production and reduce the reliance on fossil fuels. Through replacement of emissions in the production of electricity and hydrogen we estimate the total annual emissions savings potential of the MegaRoller technology at 517 million metric tons (megaton) of carbon-dioxide equivalent emissions, representing roughly 1 % of the global greenhouse gas emissions.

The single most efficient application of the MegaRoller technology for reducing carbon emissions is in a dedicated green hydrogen production system, in combination with other renewable energy sources, to displace emissions from transportation. With possible collocated sites assessed in 20 countries around the world, the annual potential production from the MegaRoller dedicated green hydrogen scheme exceeds 5 megatons of green hydrogen (some 200 TWh at low heating value²⁰), which could save upwards of 400 megatons of CO₂e in transportation applications displacing gasoline²¹.

Further considering applications in regions with low solar radiation or otherwise limited opportunities to install other VRE source (e.g. islands with limited land area) the MegaRoller technology can be used to supply electricity directly to the grid. Assuming displacement of pulverized coal in these remote areas, the MegaRoller technology could displace 19 megatons of CO₂e emissions annually.

Another potential source of emissions displacement considered is the application of the technology in other WECs. There are various regions and environments with ample wave energy resource, but which cannot be viably captured or utilized by the MegaRoller technology. Considering the possibilities of the MegaRoller PTO to be applied in alternative WEC designs the emissions reduction potential may be expanded to cover the impact these solutions would have once fully industrialized. Assuming equivalent production efficiencies and utilization of less than a fifth of the total potential wave energy resource beyond the reach of the MegaRoller WEC, we estimate other WECs could displace up to 100 megatons of CO₂e.

3.3 Renewable electricity

Wave energy in the form of the surge phenomenon, that is utilized by the MegaRoller, is present throughout oceanic regions around the world, and increasingly more predominant further from the equator. Upon reaching the coastline the water particles are in a unidirectional motion and the energy expressed in a metric kilowatts per meter. The distribution of wave power around the world is presented in Figure 2. Applied in the context of OWSC, the global distribution and availability of the wave energy

¹⁹ Mørk, G. et al. (2010) Assessing the Global Wave Energy Potential

²⁰ European Commission, DG-Energy (2020) Hydrogen generation in Europe: Overview of key costs and benefits

²¹ The estimate on emissions displacement in transportation factors in assumptions of manufacturing, usage and the relative efficiencies of combustion engines and hydrogen fuel cell electric vehicles

resource establishes the geographical boundaries for the commercial applications of the MegaRoller technology.

Figure 2 Annual wave power worldwide²²

Demand for renewable energy sources in global markets is increasing at rapid pace due to the requirement for emission reductions. Currently the demand is satisfied almost solely by wind and PV power due to their cost competitiveness reached during recent years. As the total share of the wind and PV power generation in most power systems is still relatively low, the installation of new variable renewable sources is technically relatively straightforward. However, as the share of adjustable power generation capacity in the grid diminishes and the share of wind and PV generation becomes dominant form of power generation, further addition of wind and solar becomes increasingly troublesome both from economical and technical perspectives.

As local wind and solar power generation are weather dependent, the addition of new capacity will increase production during high resource conditions but provide little support to meet the power demand when the winds die out and solar irradiation is blocked. Therefore, the fluctuation in electricity availability and consequently, costs are increased. With additional power supply, the value of electricity of all wind and PV assets in the system generating at the same time are reduced – an effect called prize cannibalization. Consequently, maintaining power supply during times of deficient renewable availability is increasingly expensive without complementary power sources²³. Therefore, it can be deduced that LCOE of a variable renewable technology no longer illustrates accurately the actual value of variable renewable power sources.

In a system with high quantities of wind and PV, MegaRoller can generate higher relative profits per generated unit of energy with generation schedule landing to times of deficient power availability. The higher the relative share of other variable power sources is in the power system, the higher the electricity price fluctuation and profitability for MegaRoller technology. The addition of the MegaRoller technology to an energy mix containing wind and PV also reduces capacity requirement for more expensive energy

²² Mørk, G. et al. (2010) Assessing the Global Wave Energy Potential

²³ Sepulveda, N. et al. (2018) The role of firm low-carbon electricity resources in deep decarbonization of power generation

storage systems and rapid response generation. Consequently, a more significant decarbonization of power system can be achieved with lower total costs. Because of the cannibalization effect induced by high share of wind and PV and the related increased value of MegaRoller energy, the MegaRoller technology reaches commercial status at higher relative technology cost compared to wind and PV technologies.

The industrialized countries and states with the highest potential demand for the MegaRoller WEC in electricity generation are presented in Table 1. Future potential is speculated through the addition of low-carbon power generation capacity required to decarbonize the country or state. It is assumed that the total annual power generation must be doubled to reach carbon neutrality due to increased electrification²⁴, and the existing fossil-based capacity and the increasing electricity demand are covered by new low-carbon technologies.

Table 1. Electricity generation in addressable markets for the MegaRoller (TWh)²⁵

Country / area	Annual electricity generation	Addition of low-carbon capacity by 2050
France	529	534
UK	318	493
California (US)	278	400
Spain	259	362
Australia	243	428
South Africa	234	462
Norway	148	150
Washington (US)	117	146
British Columbia (CA)	74	78
Chile	73	116
Oregon (US)	61	84
Portugal	57	75
Mexico	57	110
Peru	50	73
New Zealand	43	51
Ireland	31	50
Morocco	29	48
Iceland	18	21
Total	2 619	3 681

Although approximating doubling power generation is very rough, the increase in electricity demand due to electrification will be significant. With these assumptions the 2050 demand for electricity in the presented locations, and the total addressable market for the MegaRoller WEC would surmount to roughly 3 700 TWh/year. Considering the energy resource and the technical and practical limitations of the technology the MegaRoller WEC could service up to 3 % of this market.

Expanding the market potential to all countries with an applicable wave energy resource and a sufficient power demand, the total quantity of the MegaRoller units to satisfy the serviceable market would be approximately 70 000.

²⁴ SITRA (2021) Enabling cost-efficient electrification in Finland.

²⁵ Industrialized countries with notable electricity demand

3.4 Frequency and power management

The existence of frequency containment markets varies depending on the country. In some countries renewables still contribute to only a marginal share in the power systems and thus, have not created a marketplace for frequency regulation. As the amount of variable power generation in the grid increases, it can be expected that the markets for frequency support services continue to expand and evolve. It is likely that frequency regulation markets will emerge in some form in all countries with significant share of VRE capacity. Additionally, the size of existing markets could be expected to increase along the requirement for frequency management.

Besides actual frequency containment in markets, the MegaRoller fleet could also be used for power balance management of wind or PV plant output. In several countries with high shares of renewable power installations, the grid codes already include an item regarding the maximum ramp rate of power injected to the grid.²⁶ Due to these ramp rate regulations utility-scale VRE systems typically require an additional energy storage to suppress the worst-case power variation. Batteries are the most typical choice for such activities however, the MegaRoller WEC can also provide power balance management services for VRE systems.

The additional investment to battery capacity could be replaced partly or fully by the MegaRoller. The extent of the battery replacement potential depends on the considered grid regulations and the wave energy resource. As MegaRollers can suppress the power fluctuation of other VRE, the capital can be used in additional power generation capacity instead of energy storage capacity. Thus, the investment would lead to increased renewable power generation and revenue, in addition to satisfying the grid code.

An analysis of future frequency market potential was conducted to assess the size of the required reserves in the countries represented in Table 1. The country specific fast frequency reserve requirements are estimated based on the current fast frequency reserves in the Nordic power system²⁷. The ratio between fast frequency reserve to the annual electricity generation is assumed constant and used to determine the reserve requirements. The calculations are based on the future demand estimates for annual power generation for each region.

Table 2. Frequency reserve markets in addressable regions for the MegaRoller

Country / Area	Status of current markets	Future potential (MW)
France / Central Europe ²⁸	Operational	794
UK	Operational	477
California (US)	Operational	417
Spain	Operational	388
Australia	Operational	365
South Africa	Vertically integrated utility	352
Norway	Operational	222
Washington (US)	Vertically integrated utilities	175
British Columbia (CA)	Vertically integrated utilities	111
Chile	No markets	110
Oregon (US)	Vertically integrated utilities	91
Mexico	Operational	86

²⁶ Martins, J. et al. (2019) Comparative Study of Ramp-Rate Control Algorithms for PV with Energy Storage Systems

²⁷ FINGRID, Reserves and balancing power

²⁸ France is part of Central European Frequency Containment Reserve Cooperation

Portugal	Operational	85
Peru	No markets	75
New Zealand	Operational	64
Ireland	Operational	46
Morocco	Vertically integrated utility	43
Iceland	Operational	27
Total		3 928

Many of the inspected countries have frequency reserve markets in some form but do not offer suitable markets for MegaRoller technology. This is because the technical requirements for the reserve assets demand excessively long periods of up-regulation. However, the countries with the most sophisticated frequency markets all include a short-term reserve for normal operation frequency maintenance.

Additionally, several countries and states support traditional energy regulations and monopolies. In the absence of liberal markets, the potential for frequency reserve markets is less straightforward to analyse. However, even monopoly utilities are required to procure frequency reserve assets when the amount of VRE installations increase. For those cases, MegaRoller could be proposed as a sustainable solution directly to the utility. On the other hand, both Chile and Peru have liberal electricity markets, but the frequency reserve markets are only in the preparation or planning stages.

Although the availability of frequency reserve markets for the MegaRoller technology is currently limited, several countries have already established plans to diversify the market platform²⁹. Many market schemes currently favour spinning reserve technologies, which are typically powered by fossil fuels. Utilities have realized that diversifying the market portfolio enables new reserve assets (including low-carbon solutions) and thus, aim to provide more accessible market platforms.

Assuming all the assessed countries would eventually form similar frequency reserve market platforms as in the Nordics, Ireland, Mexico, California, Australia or in New Zealand – the total fast frequency reserve requirement would be at least 3.9 GW. The assumptions of countries adopting such market model is not far-fetched when the VRE capacities increase to levels where maintaining electrical security in the power supply is threatened. Furthermore, the required reserve capacity might be significantly higher should the countries have larger penetration of VRE compared to current Nordic power system taken as a reference here.

3.5 Green hydrogen

Hydrogen already has significant uses in the chemical industry and especially in ammonia production and refining processes. Additionally, as described in section 2.2.2, green hydrogen can be used as a resource in multiple other industries and in thus, the demand for hydrogen is expected to increase drastically during the coming decades. Green hydrogen can be used to decarbonize industries, which are otherwise extremely dependent on fossil fuels. For example, steel manufacturing and marine transportation contribute to significant portion of global greenhouse gas emissions and are very difficult to decarbonize without use of renewable fuels. Hydrogen can be used to produce also other carbon neutral compounds such as ammonia, methane, and methanol, which are vastly used in industries.

Currently hydrogen is produced using CO₂ emitting steam methane reformation, but renewable powered water electrolysis is expected to cover a significant share of future hydrogen demand. The challenge in

²⁹ National Grid ESO, Future of balancing services; The Australian Energy Market Commission, Fast frequency response market ancillary service

satisfying the demand with renewable hydrogen to date is related to reaching sufficiently production cost levels. A production cost of 1–2 EUR/kg_{H₂} is considered the level which enables commercial applications for green hydrogen in most industries. Major contributors to hydrogen production costs are the electrolyzer technology and renewable energy. Additionally, the capacity factor of the electrolyzer is susceptible to input power variation. Two approaches are typically exploited to mediate power variation and increase the capacity factor for the process: oversizing the renewable power generation capacity with respect to the electrolyzer capacity, and the usage of multiple power sources with varying generation schedules. The MegaRoller technology can be a key contributor in satisfying the increasing renewable power demand in hydrogen sector through the value-added described in chapter 2. Additionally, it reduces the requirement for oversized generation capacity leading to reduced costs related to power generation.

Markets for green hydrogen are expected to increase dramatically especially in the developed and industrialized countries. For example, the EU and US have both recently announce hydrogen strategies, which aim to transform the societies towards independency from fossil fuels³⁰. In the first phase of the EU hydrogen strategy (from 2020 to 2024) the objective is to install 6 GW of electrolyzer capacity. In the second phase, for 2030 the target is 40 GW and annual hydrogen production of 10 Mt_{H₂}. The primary purpose in the initial stages of the strategy is to replace natural gas -based production in the existing hydrogen uses. Gradually the sector will be developed to satisfy demand in other use-cases, e.g. in heavy transportation and industry.

Similar to European strategy, a hydrogen plan has also been published by the US Department of Energy with a mission to research, develop and validate hydrogen technologies for commercial adoption in multiple sectors. Distinct from the EU hydrogen strategy, the US strategy aims to develop hydrogen technologies to enable technical and cost readiness for commercial applications. Hence, the program primarily aims for technological development and sets no objectives related to market development. Nevertheless, green hydrogen is set to expand rapidly also in the US.

Noting that also Australia³¹, Canada³², South Africa³³, and Chile³⁴ have their own national hydrogen strategies the market potential for utilizing MegaRoller in green hydrogen production is significant. As majority of the regions with applicable wave energy resources have published hydrogen-related strategies the marketing of the MegaRoller solution can be focused on these areas bearing in mind both electricity and hydrogen production services.

3.6 Freshwater

Today, there is an unprecedented pressure on global water resources. The World Bank estimates that with current practices the world will face a 40 % shortfall between forecast demand and available supply of water by 2030³⁵. Agricultural production consumes 70% of global water resources today and by 2050 will require a 60% increase to feed growing global population with a 15% increase in water withdrawals. In addition to the increasing demand, access to freshwater is already limited in many parts of the world

³⁰ European Commission (2020) A hydrogen strategy for a climate-neutral Europe; US Department of Energy (2020) Hydrogen Strategy, Enabling A Low-Carbon Economy

³¹ COAG Energy Council (2019) Australia's National Hydrogen Strategy

³² https://www.nrcan.gc.ca/sites/www.nrcan.gc.ca/files/environment/hydrogen/NRCan_Hydrogen-Strategy-Canada-na-en-v3.pdf

³³ <https://hysainfrastructure.com/>

³⁴ https://energia.gob.cl/sites/default/files/national_green_hydrogen_strategy_-_chile.pdf

³⁵ World Bank (2017) Water Resource Management

with estimates indicating that 40% of the world population live in water scarce areas, and approximately a quarter of world's GDP is exposed to this challenge.

Desalination of sea water ranks among the most expensive of water supply options, however there are over 150 countries that use the technology to supply water demand and the globally installed desalination capacity has been growing linearly for the past 15 years. In 2018, 18,426 desalination plants were in operation worldwide, producing 86.5 million cubic meters of clean water each day and supplying freshwater to over 300 million people. Historically multi-flash distillation has been the most widely adopted technology for water desalination however, during the 21st century this has been widely replaced by reverse osmosis which today accounts for the majority of the new installed desalination capacity. The historical evolution in global desalination capacity is presented in Figure 3

Figure 3 Historical development of global water desalination installations ³⁶

The increasing demand for desalination is expected continue as water consumption increases and existing water resources are further impacted by global warming. Desalination is an energy-intensive process, and the RO plants are designed to operate at constant load and with a grid connection. As such majority of them are primarily run with fossil-fuel based production thereby contributing to the very causes of the problem whose impacts they are deployed to mitigate. As future energy systems are most likely powered by VRE, it is essential that water desalination as an energy intensive industry would be capable of operation under variable loads. However, the fast transients of wind and PV power generation creates challenges for technology adaptation.

The water desalination markets applicable to the MegaRoller technology are listed in Table 3.. Each country on the list is impacted by droughts and water scarcity. Here, only seawater reverse osmosis plants close to potential MegaRoller WEC sites have been included. For example, Spain has significant amount of operational desalination capacity, but none close to potential MegaRoller WEC site.

³⁶ <https://fronteirasxxi.pt/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/The-state-of-desalination-and-brine-production-A-global-outlook.pdf>

Furthermore, roughly half of the global desalination capacity is located in the Middle East and North Africa region where wave energy resource for the MegaRoller WEC is insufficient.

Table 3. Capacities and respective electrical loads of the current addressable water desalination market

Country	Water production capacity (m3/day)	Power consumption range (MW)
Australia	1 110 000	160-210
Chile	510 000	75-95
Morocco	350 000	51-66
Mexico	210 000	31-40
California	200 000	30-38
Peru	37 000	5-7
South Africa	21 000	3-4
Total	2 438 000	356-457

As extended droughts become more frequent, the requirement of desalination capacity in these countries will increase. This has already been witnessed in several countries during the past few years, for example in Chile and Peru both countries which now aim to significantly increase the share of RO desalination in freshwater supply. New regions may also become exposed to freshwater scarcity, for example in Algarve where Portugal have been forced to consider water desalination due to droughts.

4 BUSINESS CASES

Although OWSCs work well in a wide range of wave climates and frequencies, the most economic business cases for the technology are aligned with the geographical locations where the energy resource is the strongest. The MegaRoller WEC with its up-scaled capacity is especially advantageous in areas with the highest wave resource as it can most efficiently exploit the whole spectrum of the resource.

Two business cases are considered for projects utilizing the MegaRoller WEC. Case A is a small-scale pilot project for the production of electricity in the Irish energy markets and case B, a similar small-scale concept for Portugal with the distinction that power generation is dedicated to green hydrogen production.

4.1 Case A: 8 MW Ireland – electricity

The electricity grid in Ireland is mostly isolated, with only two points of connection across to Great Britain and onwards to the rest of Europe. As a result of this isolation, the grid within Ireland needs capabilities to manage the grid frequency and ensure reliable supply of electricity across the island. There is currently a high amount of wind energy used to supply the grid in Ireland, which results in some issues with grid stability. Coal power production is used to fill the gap when the wind resource is insufficient, however this suffers from a timing lag (to ramp up the generator at the coal plant) and a negative carbon impact.

The average consumer price for electricity during the period 2008 to 2020 has varied between 100 EUR/MWh and 140 EUR/MWh³⁷. The Irish government has recently introduced the Renewable Energy Support Scheme³⁸, which will provide EUR 7.2–12.5 billion in support for green power production over a period of 15 years³⁹.

The coastline of Ireland is fully exposed to the Northern Atlantic Ocean and receives a high amount of wave energy along the western and north-western coasts. The southern coasts receive some wave energy, while the eastern coast is relatively protected. The wave resource on the western coast can reach an annual average of up to 74 kW/m and is impacted by the local geographic and bathymetric conditions. In many places the bathymetry becomes deep relatively quickly, which limits the potential sites for deployment of MegaRoller devices.

The potential site for this project is along the coastline near Killard. The average wave resource remains strong (44 kW/m) without being extreme. This results in an adequate power generation potential while enabling suitable weather windows for delivery and maintenance activities. Additionally, there are suitable locations for the manufacturing and assembly of the devices MegaRoller devices. The existence of high-quality supply chain nearby is beneficial both to the economics of the project as well as for the local community through creation of jobs and increased economic activity.

³⁷ <https://www.seai.ie/data-and-insights/seai-statistics/key-statistics/prices/>

³⁸ <https://www.eirgridgroup.com/customer-and-industry/renewable-electricity-support-scheme/>

³⁹ <https://www.energylivenews.com/2020/07/21/eu-approves-irelands-new-renewable-aid-scheme/>

Figure 4 Cliffs of Moher in County Clare, Ireland

Figure 5 Illustration of a wave farm

Power production in the coast near Killard was simulated using wave timeseries data, technical characteristics of the MegaRoller PTO, and a corresponding panel design. The average annual power generation for an 8 MW wave farm would be approximately 19 200 MWh. Using the information on the local electricity pricing, the annual income would range between 1 920 000 EUR and 2 688 000 EUR.

Potential frequency support services in the Irish electricity markets were also analysed in addition to power generation. Fast frequency reserve services in Ireland could provide an additional income of 992 000 – 1 368 000€/year. It can be expected that the frequency support markets offer even larger potential as the amount of VRE increases in the Irish power system and the frequency support markets are evolved⁴⁰.

Based on these estimates, the total annual income with current electricity cost levels would range between EUR 2.9 million and EUR 4.1 million, and the project would achieve a reasonable payback period and a relative high rate of return.

In relation to the site in question, it is of note that an Ireland-based ocean energy project development company Simply Blue Energy are developing a combined wave and floating wind project in the same region. The project envisions floating wind capacity of 1 GW (targeted to be operational by 2032), and a wave energy portion of 30 MW. The WECs are planned to be deployed in two phases with a 5 MW by 2026 and 25 MW by 2028.⁴¹

4.2 Case B: 5 MW Portugal – hydrogen

Portugal has an integrated electricity grid with Spain, and onwards to the rest of Europe and to Northern Africa. Currently these interconnections outside of Iberia are of limited capacity, resulting in some islanding effects within Iberia. The entirety of the western coast of Portugal is subjected to a good wave resource and the solar irradiation is also substantial due to the geographic location and a relatively dry climate. The average offshore wave energy resource ranges from 16 kW/m to 38 kW/m at various points along the Portuguese coastline, with the highest resource on the coast near Ericeira to Leiria.

⁴⁰ Grid connection and system services of a wave power plant - a case study

⁴¹ <https://www.westernstarmarine.com/>

The consumer price for electric energy in Portugal during the period 2008 to 2019 has varied between 68 EUR/MWh and 118 EUR/MWh⁴². Previously there were large renewable energy subsidies provided in Portugal, mainly in the form of FITs, however no direct support mechanisms remain. This impacts the ability for new renewable energy technologies to compete – both against traditional generation methods (e.g. gas and coal) and established renewable methods (e.g. wind, solar). To increase the competitiveness of the MegaRoller solution in Portugal and demonstrate its value-added, the production of green hydrogen was considered for the case in addition to participating in electricity markets.

Portugal have also announced a EUR 7 billion national hydrogen strategy to move towards a hydrogen economy with the goal of increasing the share of hydrogen in final energy consumption to 5 % by 2030⁴³. In practise this means increasing the share of the energy originating from renewable power sources and reducing the dependence on imported fossil fuels. By 2030, the goal for Portugal is to install at least 2 GW of electrolysis capacity, and the share of hydrogen as a power source in road transportation should increase to 20 %.

The site for this business case is near Peniche, in the same location used by AW-Energy for deployment of the WaveRoller demonstration device (2012-2014) and WaveRoller FOAK device (2019-present). As the necessary licenses for the site have been obtained and there is significant prior operational experience from the site, the extension of site with MegaRoller WEC units is relatively straightforward.

Figure 6 WaveRoller demonstration device

Figure 7 WaveRoller FOAK device

For case B the installation of five MegaRoller WEC units with a single PTO each are considered, and a PV plant as a complementary power source. The varying availability of the resources complements each other leading to an increased electrolyzer load factor and higher annual hydrogen production. The capacity for PV plant is set to 5MW and the electrical capacity of the electrolyzer is also set to 5MW. Thus, the nominal power generating capacity of the system is 10 MW in total while the load is 5 MW. A 5 MW link to the utility grid is also considered to enable dispatchment of power to markets. To ensure hydrogen is produced solely with renewable power, energy flow is allowed only towards the grid.

Like with case A, the power generation of the MegaRoller WECs in Peniche were estimated based on wave timeseries data. PV power generation was modelled using similar approach with irradiation timeseries. The simulation resulted in annual hydrogen production of 350 metric tons. Additionally, 1 174 MWh of electricity was dispatched to the grid per year. Total annual income from sales of hydrogen

⁴² <https://www.statista.com/statistics/595841/electricity-industry-price-portugal/>

⁴³ <https://www.iea.org/policies/12436-hydrogen-strategy?country=Portugal&qs=portugal>

and electricity would range between EUR 1.8 million and EUR 3.6 million assuming a hydrogen retail price of 5-10 EUR and the electricity prices state above. The variance in the annual income is relatively large due to the high uncertainties of future electricity and green hydrogen retail prices.

The annual spread of hydrogen and power production with the considered capacities is presented in Figure 8. The complimentary nature of MegaRoller and PV production is notable as no significant variation of hydrogen production is present throughout the whole year. On occasion, the annual average is exceeded during winter and spring months as the wave energy resource peaks however, power is injected to the grid mostly to the summer months with significantly higher PV production.

Figure 8 Case B: monthly hydrogen and power production

Part of the annual variation in the excess power production can also be explained by the fluctuating nature of PV production. In the summer months, the generation of a PV plant typically reaches its nominal capacity during the daytime while declining to zero when the sun sets. In practice, this results in excess power during daytime whilst the electrolyzers rely completely on wave energy during the night. Similar power fluctuations don't occur with wave energy leading to the MegaRoller WECs producing power much more consistently. This leads to a more stable operation environment for the electrolyzer, which increases the stack lifetime and the performance of the system.

Figure 9 Load profiles of the hydrogen system during winter and summer months

The operation of the system during one week in the winter and summer months is illustrated in Figure 9. The MegaRoller technology can provide a stable baseload for the electrolyzer while the variation of PV production is significantly higher. The load factor for the electrolyzers in the modelled case approached 50 %, which is significantly higher compared to a system powered only with solar PV, due the complimentary nature of wind and wave energy both a daily and on a seasonal basis.

5 ELEMENTS OF THE COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS

The following tables set out elements considered in a cost-benefit analysis of a MegaRoller WEC project. Suggested measures for assessing the value or cost of the different elements are also included.

Table 4. Benefits from a MegaRoller wave farm

Benefit	Measure
Production of clean, renewable electricity: The largest benefit from the installation of a MegaRoller WEC project is the production of electricity. This will be fed into the local electricity grid at the relevant local tariff or used for the production of hydrogen or freshwater, generating a financial benefit.	Forecast energy production multiplied by commodity prices
Out of phase electricity production: The wave resource in the northern hemisphere is highest during the winter and can balance lower PV resource during that season. In addition, the wave resource is available both day and night, closer to baseload power than other VRE sources.	Comparison to costs of alternative approaches (e.g. gas peaking plants, battery storage)
Reduced cannibalisation of returns: Whilst the new development costs of wind and solar are pressing down the energy prices, the increased production capacity of these technologies also accumulates electricity production at times when these resources peak ⁴⁴ . This results in a further price drop in the commodity and lower returns for all energy assets delivering power to the market at that time, i.e. the cannibalization effect. Production using alternative renewable resources, such as wave energy, can reduce or avoid this cannibalization effect.	Estimates of cannibalization effect costs which are avoided by using wave energy
Frequency support: The energy storage capabilities within MegaRoller allow rapid adjustment of the electricity supplied to the grid. This can be used to assist in stabilising the grid frequency, for example at times when the wind resource drops off quickly. This benefit will become more important as more VRE are installed in an energy system.	Financial compensation from grid operator for providing frequency support
Power supply for industries: Predictability of the wave resource and the consistent power output of MegaRoller WECs is beneficial for various inflexible processes. MegaRoller enable smoother transition of industries to fully renewable-based operation. For example, water desalination and green hydrogen production industries benefit from high predictability and consistency of power supply.	Higher compensation from e.g. PPA contracts due to high predictability and consistency
Local manufacturing: Significant elements of the MegaRoller WEC device can be manufactured locally through standard steel and concrete manufacturing processes, thereby providing jobs to the local population.	Value of local manufacturing plus local multiplier effect
Compliance with sustainable finance taxonomy: The carbon impact from a MegaRoller WEC device has been assessed to be 33.8g CO ₂ e/kWh, well below the thresholds set by the EU's Sustainable Finance Taxonomy. This allows projects using the MegaRoller technology to receive funding from sustainable investment funds and similar facilities.	Difference in financing cost due to using sustainable investment funds
Making use of an underutilised zone: The MegaRoller WEC is located in a depth area which is relatively underutilised. They are far enough offshore	Avoided opportunity cost compared to using other (utilised) zones

⁴⁴ Prol, J., Steiniger, K. & Zilberman, D. (2017) The Cannibalization Effect of Wind and Solar in the California Wholesale Electricity Market

that recreational users (swimmers, surfers, etc.) do not go, while being still in the nearshore environment and therefore out of shipping lanes.	
Stimulated local marine ecosystem: Although MegaRoller devices are a foreign presence in the ocean environment, they can assist in stimulating the local marine life. The devices act as artificial reefs, providing an anchor point for sea flora (which might not otherwise be present, in a sandy environment) and resting places for sea fauna. The effects have been noted with previous deployments of the WaveRoller devices, resulting in increased catch by small-scale local fishermen when the devices have been deployed.	Increased catch for local fishery activities

Table 5. Elements to assess the costs of a MegaRoller wave farm

Cost Element	Measure
Capital expenditure: The financial cost for the MegaRoller devices, assembly and installation work, and other related infrastructure work constitute the largest (and most tangible) costs for the project.	Financial expenditure
Operational expenditure: Once the devices are installed and operational, there will be ongoing costs for monitoring and maintaining the devices. This cost will be relatively constant during the lifetime of the project, with increases at the times of periodical maintenance.	Financial expenditure
Decommissioning: At the end of the lifetime of the MegaRoller devices, there will be a financial cost associated with removing the devices and disposing of the components. For many elements, it will be possible to recycle or sell for scrap purposes, which will assist in reducing the overall decommissioning cost. It might also be possible use the foundation structure in new MegaRoller devices.	Financial expenditure
Presence on sea floor: As with any electricity generation device, MegaRoller involves placing a foreign object into the environment – in this case the sea floor. This can have an impact on the local environment and needs to be appropriately monitored.	Estimate of impacts on local marine life
Societal impact: The installed devices are an obstacle within the ocean environment, which the local community will need to avoid. Although the devices are in a relatively underutilised zone (see benefits), there could be potential impact on fishery activities and tourism. These factors should be taken into account when determining the location of the project and micro-siting of the individual devices.	Estimate of impact on local population

6 DISCUSSION

The MegaRoller project has focused on the design, demonstration and validation of the PTO for OWSC technologies. The PTO is the core technical component in wave energy devices responsible for power conversion, and in OWSCs the PTO interacts with other technology components – primarily with a panel that determines power capture, the foundation structure anchoring the device in place at sea and the remainder of the plant infrastructure.

Designs for the MegaRoller WEC panel, the foundation solution and the surrounding plant infrastructure have been conceptualized during the MegaRoller project but not manufactured or validated. Further efforts are required on the design of these elements to fully realise the benefits of the MegaRoller WEC technology.

Full-scale global delivery of MegaRoller WEC fleets also requires extensive supply chain networks. The main subsystems (i.e. PTO, foundation, and panel) are considerable physical structures and thus, require special arrangements for delivery, assembly and installation. Forming an efficient and broad delivery network is crucial in maintaining low cost of delivery and technical feasibility of installation. Furthermore, the lead time of the delivery can be reduced when the supply chain fully development and optimized for the use-case.

In addition to the technical limitations, the markets for the different commercial applications of the MegaRoller technology are in a state of unprecedented change. Even though the global energy transition seems inevitable, the ultimate path to low carbon societies is still uncertain as the transition only beginning. The role of hydrogen, various energy sources, and the development of future markets mechanisms are uncertain. For these reasons, also the markets for the MegaRoller WEC are under constant change and thus, the business model for the industrialization of the technology must be able to adapt.